

The transport and retention of passive particles in Sydney Harbour and Botany Bay

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1 Introduction

The transport by the ocean of passive particles from one region to another is currently an important area of research. Examples of such particles include nutrients, propagules (e.g. larvae, spores or eggs) and pollutants. Accumulation or retention of these particles in an estuary could be important to describe in relation to mitigating impacts (e.g. oil spills, eutrophication), or understanding ecological processes (e.g. the transport of native or invasive propagules). Estuaries are highly productive and provide a diverse range of habitats for many species. Many estuaries and coastal regions in general are under increasing anthropogenic pressure due to coastal development and associated activities such as boating and shipping (Halpern *et al.*, 2008).

Port Jackson (Sydney Harbour) and Botany Bay are two of the most developed estuaries in NSW, Australia. Nearly 25% of Australia's population live in Sydney (i.e. ~ 4.3 million people) and many are concentrated around Port Jackson and Botany Bay. These estuaries are receiving bodies for urban runoff and industrial waste waters from numerous sources, such as refineries, stormwater, sewage overflows, shipping ports and agriculture. Major oil spills have also occurred in both estuaries. Impacts of decades of large pollutant loads into Port Jackson from industry came to a head in February 2006 when bans were placed on commercial fishing due to dangerously high levels of total dioxins and furans accumulating in commercially and recreationally important species (Birch *et al.*, 2007).

Estuaries are also the major entry point for marine invasive species, either attached to the hulls of ships and boats, through the release of ballast water from larger vessels, or in association with aquaculture infrastructure (Allen, 1953; Williams *et al.*, 1988; Ruiz *et al.*, 1997). The biota transferred through ballast water, for example, is thought to exceed 10 000 species daily across the globe (Streftaris *et al.*, 2005). Given that invasive species cannot be excluded from our estuaries, eradication or control of problematic invaders will often depend on a rapid response to any incursion. Paramount for any rapid response plan is good information about where a species might spread from its initial point of incursion. One of the aims of this study was, therefore, to model the likely dispersal of larvae of

invasive marine species that could arrive on vessels entering the two major Sydney ports. To this end, we implement a new particle dispersion technique to investigate the transport of passive particles in Port Jackson and Botany Bay.

Port Jackson is a microtidal, well-mixed estuary in south-east Australia with a mean volume of $5.11 \times 10^8 \text{ m}^3$, covering an area of $5.17 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^2$ (Figure 1). The tidal range is 0.5 m (Neap) to 2.2 m (Spring), with little variation in range or phase from the mouth to the upper reaches of the Parramatta River (22.5 km upstream). The entrance to Sydney Harbour is wide ($\sim 3 \text{ km}$) and deep ($\sim 30 \text{ m}$) with no significant bar or sill. The bathymetry is complex with deep basins ($\sim 28 \text{ m}$) and shallow areas with depths $< 3.5 \text{ m}$ with an average depth of 9.9 m. Typically freshwater inflow (which is dependent entirely on rainfall) is low and flushing is primarily dominated by the M2 tide (Das *et al.*, 2000). Stratification can occur through seasonal heating or cooling and sporadic local rainfall run off. Over the last two years, an average of 264 international vessels (primarily commercial) arrived in Port Jackson (Australian Customs Service unpubl. data).

Botany Bay is a microtidal estuary also located within the Greater Metropolitan Sydney, situated approximately 20 km south of Port Jackson (Figure 1). Botany Bay is home to several industrial sites surrounding its shorelines including oil refineries, Sydney Airport, the runways of which extend into the bay, and Australia's second largest container port (Port Botany), which handles approximately one third of Australia's container trade and is currently under expansion to accommodate the increasing demand on the port (NSW Department of Planning, 2008). Arrivals of international vessels into Port Botany average 590 per year over the last two years (Australian Customs Service unpubl. data).

The entrance to Botany Bay is also deep ($\sim 20 \text{ m}$) and the narrowest width of the entrance is approximately 1 km. The maximum length (width) of the bay is 8.8 km (7.8 km). Botany Bay covers an area of $4.03 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^2$ with a mean volume of $234 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$, (excluding contribution from the Georges River). The bathymetry is less complicated than Port Jackson, with a deep (dredged) channel between the entrance to Botany Bay and Port Botany ($\sim 20 \text{ m}$), while the remainder of the bay is predominately shallow with depths $< 5 \text{ m}$.

Here we address the question of the transport and retention of passive particles in both Sydney Harbour and Botany Bay using configurations of the Princeton Ocean Model (POM). Different forcing conditions are simulated (wind and tide) and various release points are investigated, some of which are likely release points for propagules of invasive species. We investigate the age of the water within each of the estuaries and the residence times of particles at each release point. Conclusions are drawn regarding the implications for the transport of pollutants under different forcing conditions.

2 Model Configuration

We have used a configuration of the Princeton Ocean Model (POM) applied to both Sydney Harbour (SH) and Port Botany (BB). POM is a three-dimensional, free surface, sigma co-ordinate, primitive equation model described in detail by Blumberg and Mellor (1987); Mellor (1996). Following Das *et al.* (2000) *inter alia* we use the two-dimensional mode of the three-dimensional model to investigate the tidal circulation within Port Jackson and Botany Bay. This is justified as density variations tend to be small (Roughan, unpublished data), except as mentioned above after (rare) periods of heavy rainfall.

2.1 Model Grid and Bathymetry

The domain of the SH model (Figure 2) extends from the mouth of Sydney Harbour to 22.5 km west, along the Parramatta River. A high resolution model was configured, with 445 grid boxes along the east-west axis of the estuary and 231 grid boxes along the north-south axis, where $\Delta x = \Delta y = 50$ m. The high resolution model we have used is an improvement on the work by Das *et al.* (2000), both in resolution and in extent towards the head of the Paramatta River.

The domain of the BB model (Figure 3) extends from the mouth of the bay 6 km west to the entrance of Georges River but does not include the Georges River itself (due to its shallow nature and the implications for wetting and drying). The BB model consists of 91

grid boxes along both the x' and y' axes with $\Delta x = \Delta y = 100$ m where the x' and y' axes refer to a clockwise rotation of 50° from the east-west and north-south axes respectively, to simplify boundary conditions. Note that all figures of Botany Bay presented here have been rotated back into the east-west and north-south orientation. Both the SH and BB models were configured with 6 vertical sigma (σ) levels with an internal timestep of $\delta t = 60$ sec.

2.2 Forcing M2 tide, η

Sealevel forcing is applied at the eastern boundary of the SH model domain and the positive x' boundary of the BB domain. An analysis of M2 tidal amplitudes obtained for 2006 (BODC) showed that the mean tidal amplitude was 0.501 m (i.e a range of 1.02 m) at Fort Denison (Sydney Harbour). In an investigation of the residual circulation within Sydney Harbour, Das *et al.* (2000) showed that inclusion of the S2 tide did not significantly change the residual circulation. Hence an M2 tidal forcing was applied at the eastern boundary with an amplitude of 0.501 m. For a direct comparison, the Botany Bay model was subjected to the same tidal forcing, given by:

$$\eta = 0.501 \sin(\omega t)$$

Where ω is given by the frequency of the M2 tide, with a period of 12.42 h.

Output from the SH model showed up to a 13 % variation in the tidal amplitude at different locations within the harbour, with the amplitude increasing with distance from the heads, being 0.501 m at the harbour entrance, to 0.569 m in the Parramatta River and 0.512 m in Bantry Bay. There is a phase lag of up to 21.4 min (20.1 min) during the ebb (flood) tidal phase at the Parramatta River and a lag of 5.6 min (5.3 min) in Bantry Bay compared to the mouth of SH.

In contrast to SH, the BB model showed a small tidal phase lag at different areas within the Bay with less than a 4 min lag between the tidal elevation at the entrance to Botany Bay, and that at the Georges River. The variation in tidal amplitude was also much

smaller than that experienced in Sydney Harbour, with the amplitude at Georges River being 0.512 m. Both the phase lag and tidal amplitude increase as one moves further west into Botany Bay. This highlights one of the main differences in the tidal influences on SH and BB. In SH for example the tide propagates through the head and up the Parramatta River, where as in BB, the effect is more of a simultaneous rise and fall in sea level (like a paddle) throughout the entire bay.

2.3 Wind Forcing

Observations of wind speed and direction were obtained for two Sydney locations, Observatory Hill (SH) and Sydney Airport (BB) from the Australian Bureau of Meteorology (Table 1). Analysis of this data shows that the Sydney region experiences predominantly a land breeze (westerly wind) and sea breeze (northeasterly wind) system from spring to early autumn with winds strengthening each afternoon, while in winter offshore (westerly) winds dominate. The strongest winds are from the south associated with the passage of low pressure systems, predominantly during winter. Based on this information (Table 1), for the purposes of our model simulations we chose six wind scenarios: no wind, easterly, westerly, southerly northerly and north easterly with a mean wind speed of 14.5 kmh^{-1} ($\sim 0.05 \text{ Pa}$). Unless stated otherwise we have used the meteorological convention to define wind direction, i.e. the direction the wind is coming from.

3 Results

3.1 Model Velocities

The movement of water in SH predominately occurs in the main channels of the harbour during the flood and ebb tidal phases, with little motion in the peripheral embayments such as Rushcutters Bay and Homebush Bay (Figure 4). At both high and low tide several gyres are established within the harbour. For example, around low tide clockwise gyres

occur between North and South Heads and to the north of Rushcutters Bay under all wind scenarios. During high tide a persistent clockwise gyre is established to the south of Middle Head under each of the wind scenarios. A clockwise gyre forms to the west of North Head which is absent in the presence of a northerly wind and but strongest during southerly winds.

The effects of wind on the circulation within SH are greatest near the entrance to the harbour, particularly under northerly and southerly wind forcing (Figure 5). In these scenarios, the gyres that are present under the no-wind scenario are moved north or south at the entrance to the harbour by the along shore winds.

Model velocities throughout BB tend to be weaker than those experienced in SH, however at the entrance to both estuaries model velocities are comparable in magnitude (Figure 6). This figure also highlights the difference in velocities at the entrance to SH (BB) under the different wind scenarios. Velocities range -0.1 to 0.2 ms^{-1} (south/north) and -0.3 to 0.2 ms^{-1} (west/east) at the entrance to SH with BB velocities comparable in magnitude in the north/south direction but weaker in the westerly direction.

In BB in the absence of wind forcing (Figure 7), gyres are present during the change of tide, with a clockwise gyre being established just inside the entrance to the bay which strengthens under the influence of northerly and westerly winds but weakens in southerly winds. During low tide, an anticlockwise gyre circulates about 1 km to the northwest of the entrance, as well as another anticlockwise gyre to the west of La Perouse, both of which strengthen in easterly (Figure 8) and northeasterly winds.

Wind forcing plays a large role in determining the circulation within Botany Bay and particularly around its perimeter. The difference wind forcing scenarios tend to increase the movement of water around the coastline, allowing gyres to be established by currents meandering off into small embayments such as Port Botany and the mouth of Cooks River. This increased movement around the perimeter of Botany Bay is most prominent between Sydney Airport and the mouth of Georges River under certain wind conditions for both the ebb and flood tidal phases. During the flood tidal phase, northerly and westerly winds

move the water from Sydney Airport around to Cooks River, then south towards Georges River. In contrast, during the ebb tide, easterly (Figure 8) and southerly winds move water in the opposite direction in this area, from Georges River to the airport.

3.2 Particle Dispersion

Particle tracking schemes have been widely used in numerical models to investigate the dispersion of pollutants, larvae and other particles of interest in oceanic environments e.g. Roughan *et al.* (2003). For example, such techniques were used for the development of an ocean pollution prediction system for the movement of radionuclides into the Shimokita region in Japan using POM Kobayashi *et al.* (2002). In another study, the dispersion of early life stages of Atlantic cod in the Western Gulf of Maine was investigated using the finite volume coastal ocean model Huret *et al.* (2007).

Similarly, a particle tracking scheme has been incorporated in this study using a 2D version of the 3D particle tracking scheme available as a POM add-on. At each of the chosen locations, 1000 particles were seeded simultaneously during the middle of the flood tide, to correspond with the end of the spin up phase of the model at time $t = 1$ d. For each internal timestep of the model ($\Delta t = 60$ sec) the tracers are advected and their positions are recorded as follows:

$$x_{t+\Delta t} = x_t + (u + u')\Delta t \quad (1)$$

$$y_{t+\Delta t} = y_t + (v + v')\Delta t \quad (2)$$

where $(x, y)_t$ and $(x, y)_{t+\Delta t}$ are the tracer positions at the start and end of time step respectively, (u, v) and (u', v') are linear interpolations of the instantaneous depth averaged velocities and velocity deviations at the surrounding grid points respectively.

A new method is used here to incorporate dispersion in the particle tracking routine. The 2.5 level Mellor and Yamada turbulence closure scheme incorporated into POM is used to calculate the instantaneous turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) throughout the model domain (Mellor and Yamada, 1982). A simplified 2D version of the equation for turbulence

kinetic energy (Equation 3), where motion in the vertical has been ignored, is used with an additional assumption (Equation 4) which scales the velocity deviations in the x and y directions as a percentage of the respective velocities (u and v). The instantaneous depth averaged velocity deviations are then calculated using Equations 5 and 6.

$$TKE = \frac{1}{2} (u'^2 + v'^2) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{u'}{v'} = \frac{u}{v} \quad (4)$$

$$u' = R_x \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{kb} |u| \sqrt{\frac{2 TKE_{(k)}}{u^2 + v^2}}}{kb} \quad (5)$$

$$v' = R_y \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{kb} |v| \sqrt{\frac{2 TKE_{(k)}}{u^2 + v^2}}}{kb} \quad (6)$$

Where $TKE_{(k)}$ is the instantaneous turbulence kinetic energy for the k^{th} sigma level, (u', v') and (u, v) are the instantaneous depth averaged values of the velocity deviations and velocities respectively, $kb = 6$ represents the number of sigma levels in the model, R_x and R_y are pseudo random numbers in the x and y directions respectively calculated for each tracer at each timestep by a Fortran 77 random number generator normalised over the range $[-1 \ 1]$ with a period of 7993. Particles that leave the estuary are assumed not to return, and particles that enter land cells are ‘killed’ and are not advected further.

The modelled particle trajectories are relevant only for propagules that would remain in surface waters and we did not include any estimates of particle fall velocity. We have also assumed that propagules are essentially passive particles in that we did not consider effects of larval behaviour. Simulations are run for durations of up to 90 days to reflect the periods of time that propagules of different species could remain in the water column before settling. For example, larvae of mussels and barnacles remain in the water column for weeks or months (Thorson, 1950; Scheltema, 1986), while larvae of some ascidians and bryozoans can settle after minutes or hours (Millar, 1971; Keough and Chernoff, 1987).

3.2.1 Sydney Harbour

Four sites within Sydney Harbour were chosen from which to release particles: Rushcutters Bay, Walsh Bay, the Spit Bridge and Sow & Pigs (Figure 2) where the first three sites have well established marinas from which marine pests or pollutants could originate, and the latter site being the location of a current meter deployed by Roughan (UNSW).

The retention of particles in both Sydney Harbour (Table 2) and Botany Bay (Table 3) show a strong dependence on both the proximity of seeding to their respective entrances and to wind forcing. In Sydney Harbour, for particles seeded at Walsh Bay and Rushcutters Bay, each of the wind forcing scenarios reduced the retention of particles within the harbour, (where we use retention to include active and grounded particles). The distribution of particles released at Walsh Bay after 10, 30, 60 and 90 days is shown in Figure 9 a-d. The retention of particles seeded at Walsh Bay ranged between 52 % and 73 % after 90 d, with the lowest retention occurring under the influence of a northeasterly wind. Figure 9 e-h shows an example of the probability distribution of particles seeded at Walsh Bay under northeasterly wind forcing for 10, 30, 60 and 90 days. After as few as 10 days there is a probability (0 – 20%) that particles could be found in nearly all reaches of SH, apart from the upper extent of Middle Harbour, with only 1.6% escaping.

Figure 11 summarises the retention of particles from each of the release sites under different wind forcing scenarios. Particles seeded at Rushcutters Bay showed a larger range in retention rates, with 75 % of particles being retained for the same period of time in the no-wind scenario, whilst a westerly wind reduced the retention rate to 47 %. The particles were predominately found between Rushcutters Bay and slightly to the west of Walsh Bay. However in westerly winds, the distribution of particles moved eastward to the two adjacent embayments, Double Bay and Rose Bay.

The largest range in retention under each of the wind scenarios was found at the Spit Bridge release site, suggesting that wind plays a much greater role in the circulation of Middle Harbour than that in the main section of Port Jackson. Northerly, easterly, southerly and westerly wind scenarios increased the retention of particles seeded at the

Spit Bridge (Table 2) to a maximum retention of 56 % during the southerly wind scenario, whilst the northeasterly wind scenario reduced the retention of particles to just 3 %.

The release site at Sow & Pigs showed the smallest retention of particles of the chosen locations as one would expect with such a close proximity to the harbour entrance, particularly noting the velocity profiles in Figure 4. Less than 18 % (6 %) of particles remain in the harbour under each of the wind scenarios after just 10 (30) days. The results suggest that northerly winds strongly confine the movement of particles seeded at Sow & Pigs to the northern part of SH, restricting movement into the main section of the harbour and Middle Harbour. This suggests that the tidal excursion of new water brought in on the flood tide is restricted to within a few kilometres of the mouth of SH.

3.2.2 Botany Bay

The retention of particles seeded at Port Botany (Figure 10 a-d) ranged between 3.6 % and 34.5 % after 90 d, with the lowest (highest) retention occurring under the influence of an easterly (northerly) wind. Under a northerly wind many of the particles were trapped by the presence of an artificial revetment wall which protects Port Botany from incoming swell. Figure 10 e-h shows an example of the probability distribution of particles seeded at Port Botany under northerly wind forcing for 10, 30, 60 and 90 days. After as few as 10 days there is an 80% probability that particles will be trapped adjacent to the revetment wall along Port Botany. The retention of particles in BB shows a much greater reliance on prevailing wind conditions than in SH (see Figures 11 and 12), with at least a 30 % variation in the retention rates under the different wind scenarios at each of the release sites.

Particles seeded at Georges River showed more than a 95 % variation in the retention of particles, where all particles were retained in Botany Bay in the no-wind scenario with particles moving little distance from the position of seeding. Under the influence of northerly wind forcing, the retention rate was reduced to 84% with particles being predominately found in the southern areas of Botany Bay between Georges River and

Kurnell. Each of the other wind forcing scenarios reduced the retention rate to below 11%, with particles tending to move around the perimeter of the Bay, being predominately found in areas such as Cooks River (easterly wind forcing) and Port Botany (northeasterly wind forcing). Westerly winds resulted in the lowest retention of particles at 3 %, with a large probability of particles being found in the small embayment near Kurnell whilst still in Botany Bay.

Cooks River showed a 78 % variation in the retention of particles over a 90 d period with a maximum particle retention of 88 % occurring in southerly winds. In this wind scenario, a large proportion of the particles were found around the Cooks River region, whilst in westerly winds only 10 % of particles were retained in Botany Bay.

Compared to the no-wind scenario, northerly winds resulted in highest retention rate for particles seeded at both Sydney Airport (47 %) and Port Botany (35 %) after 90 d. Each of the other wind scenarios resulted in lower retention rates at Sydney Airport with easterly winds reducing the retention to less than 4 %. Easterly winds also significantly reduced the retention rate of particles seeded at Port Botany to 4 %. For particles seeded at Sydney Airport in the northeasterly, easterly, southerly and no-wind scenario, the particles tend to be found in the area between the airport and Port Botany. In contrast, westerly and northerly winds moved the particles towards the Cooks River, Georges River and the centre of Botany Bay. Particles seeded at Port Botany were predominately found between Port Botany and Kurnell in the no-wind scenario, whilst northerly and westerly winds increased the presence of particles in regions around the airport and Cooks River.

In the no-wind scenario, all particles seeded at Kurnell were retained in Botany Bay with most particles being found either around Kurnell, or the Cooks River. Northerly winds slightly reduced the retention rate to 93 % with the majority of the particle distribution shifting to the west of Kurnell. Each of the other wind scenarios reduced the retention rate below 13 %. The lowest retention rate occurred during westerly winds, with only 3 % of particles remaining in the bay after 90 d. Northeasterly and easterly winds resulted in the majority of particles being found around the perimeter of Botany Bay, with many particles retained around Port Botany.

3.3 The age of the water

Traditionally flushing timescales have been used to represent how quickly the water in an estuary is replaced. Various definitions exist for the flushing timescale, however typically a single number is used to describe how quickly the estuary is flushed. This however is somewhat inappropriate, as obviously the waters close to the mouth of the estuary will be flushed more quickly than the confined narrow channels near the head of an estuary. To avoid this problem we consider the age of the water within the estuary.

Unlike flushing time, age is unique to each water parcel that enters the domain of interest, hence it is spatially dependent within the model. By treating each grid box as a parcel of water, each parcel can be treated as a clock which increases in age each day. Thus the age of a parcel of water can be defined as the time that the parcel of water has spent since entering the estuary through one of its open boundaries (Monsen *et al.*, 2002).

Residence time is the compliment to age and can be defined as how long a particle or parcel of water starting at a specified location will take to exit the estuary or body of water. This is in contrast to the age of the water which is the time required for a parcel to travel from a boundary to a specified location (Monsen *et al.*, 2002). The interpretation of both age and residence time have limitations, in that they depend on the specification of the boundary, the point of interest, and in tidal systems, the phase of the tide in which parcels of water are released (Monsen *et al.*, 2002). Here we have chosen to investigate the age of the water.

The calculation of ideal age is governed by:

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{id}}{\partial t} + L(\tau_{id}) = \Theta(t - 1) \quad (7)$$

where $\tau_{id}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{t})$ is the idealised age tracer, L is a general linear transport operator, for example advection and diffusion, and $\Theta(t - 1)$ is the unit step function where $\Theta(t - 1) = 1$ for $t \geq 1$ and $\Theta(t - 1) = 0$ for $t < 1$ (Hall and Haine, 2002). This results in the water only aging after the age tracer is initialised at the end of the spin up phase of the model at $t = 1$ d.

The boundary condition imposed on the age tracer is $\tau_{id}(O, t) = 0$, where O is the open boundary of the model, which corresponds to the region where the estuary enters the ocean. The result of this boundary condition is that water which enters the estuary through the open boundary is given an age of 0 d.

The initial condition of the age tracer is given by $\tau_{id}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0}$ such that the age of the water is set to 0 d for all areas in the model at the end of the spin up phase. Throughout the model duration, water that leaves the estuary is assumed not to return and does not affect the age of any other parcels of water. As the water is advected within the harbour it mixes with other parcels of water. If for an example a parcel of water with age 0 is mixed with a parcel of equal volume of water with age 10, the resultant age of the combined parcel of water would be 5 days. As time progresses and the mixing continues the age of the water throughout the estuary establishes a quasi-steady state, where each grid box ceases to age with time. This results in spatial heterogeneity of the age of water within the estuary, which increases as distance from the estuary entrance increases, and oceanic influences are felt less.

Once the age has reached a quasi steady state there will however be small fluctuations in age throughout the tidal cycle, displayed mostly by water near the entrance of the estuary. These small variations oscillate with the frequency of the M2 tide, and their magnitude is spatially and wind dependent. On average however the age of water at all locations at a reasonable distance from the estuary entrance rises linearly until tidal flushing effects are felt, where the age begins to taper off towards a quasi steady state (See Figures 13 and 14).

3.3.1 Sydney Harbour

The age of the water in SH (Figure 13) tends to increase with increasing distance from the harbour entrance, it also increases in the small upstream embayments such as Bantry Bay and Homebush Bay (Figure 15). The maximum water age experienced in SH (~ 130 d) occurs in the Parramatta River at the western most extent of the model. The effects of

the various wind scenarios on the age of the water are evident in Figure 15. The Spit Bridge and the surrounding areas of Middle Harbour are the only areas within harbour of significant distance from the harbour entrance where certain wind conditions increase the age of water compared to the no-wind scenario. The age of water in these locations is also more sensitive to wind forcing than other areas within SH (Figure 16). The oldest water age experienced at the Spit Bridge (~ 90 d) occurs during southerly winds (Figure 15 b), which is approximately 6–12 d older than that in the no-wind scenario (Figure 16). Under each of the other wind scenarios, the age of water is reduced, with the northeasterly wind scenario producing the youngest water (~ 70 d).

Westward of Rushcutters Bay into the upper reaches of the Parramatta River the age (~ 55 d) is reduced with the presence of wind forcing (Figures 15 and 16), with the youngest water (i.e. most flushing) occurring during northeasterly and easterly winds (~ 46 d).

Westward of Rushcutters Bay into the upper reaches of the Parramatta River the age of the water is reduced with wind forcing (Figure 13 a,c,d) from ~ 55 d (~ 125 d) at Rushcutters Bay (Homebush Bay) to ~ 45 d (~ 110 d) with the youngest water occurring during NE and E winds (Figure 16 b,c). Walsh Bay which lies between Rushcutters Bay and Homebush Bay is moderately flushed. This site is significant as it encompasses the main SH shipping terminals and as such is very susceptible to the introduction of marine pests through shipping vectors.

3.3.2 Botany Bay

Water age is a maximum in BB (Figure 17) in the absence of wind forcing with the oldest water found in the weakly flushed embayment to the south of the mouth to Georges River (~ 110 d). Of note is the fact that this water is approximately 30 d younger than the oldest water observed in SH. Wind forcing decreases the age of water throughout BB except at Kurnell (due east of the bay entrance) during northerly wind forcing. Westerly winds have the greatest effect in reducing water age in the northern areas of BB (Cooks River

(14 d), Port Botany (9 d) and Sydney Airport (11 d), Figure 14 b,c,d), whilst easterly winds have the greatest effect in reducing the age by up to ~ 30 d for the southern areas of the bay (Georges River and Kurnell, Figure 14 a,e). This is in stark contrast to ages of up to ~ 100 d (~ 81 d) at the Georges (Cooks) River in the absence of wind forcing.

Of the chosen release sites Port Botany is flushed most rapidly within BB with a maximum age of just 36 d in the no-wind scenario. This is reduced to just 10 d during westerly winds. Significantly, this is the location of the main container terminal within BB which suggests any marine pests that were transported through container ships would quickly be swept out of BB into prevailing southward currents offshore of BB.

4 Conclusions and Considerations

Clearly the difference in retention patterns between SH and BB are dependent on the circulation patterns in each of the estuaries, which in turn is determined in part by the size and the geometry of the estuarine basins. SH is a drowned river valley exemplified by narrow < 1 km wide branching channels. The tide moves in and out with a narrow tidal ellipse. BB however is a wider basin where the tidal ellipses are far less constrained.

Sydney Harbour exhibits significantly older water than Botany Bay (up to 30%) which can be attributed to the small embayments and complex bathymetry of the model, in contrast to the relatively simple embayment structure of the Botany Bay configuration. This is also reflected in the retention (or flushing) of the particles.

The different wind scenarios considered here are highly idealised, however they begin to give an understanding of how wind forcing might alter the circulation within the embayments and hence the retention or transport of particles such as marine pests. That said, it is clear that the dominant forcing mechanisms is the semi diurnal tide, and flushing will vary with the range of the tide. We have considered a mean tidal range in this scenario which is representative of average conditions experienced in SH and BB. With a larger (smaller) range we would expect flushing to occur to a greater (lesser) extent.

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		Summer (DJF)		Autumn (MAM)		Winter (JJA)		Spring (SON)	
		Speed	Direction	Speed	Direction	Speed	Direction	Speed	Direction
Observatory Hill	9am	8.9	S-NE (SW)	9.1	S-NW(W)	12.8	SW-NW(W)	11.9	S-NW(W)
	3pm	18.1	S-NE (E)	13.9	S-NE (E)	15.5	S-NW(W)	18.9	S-NE(E)
Airport	9am	14.1	S (S)	12.6	SW-NW(NW)	13.4	W-NW (W)	15.8	S-NW(S)
	3pm	23.9	S-NE (NE)	18.9	S-NE (SE)	18.6	S-W (S)	24.1	S-NE (NE)
Difference	9am	5.2		3.5		0.6		3.9	
	3pm	5.8		5.0		3.1		5.2	

Table 1: Mean wind speed (kmh^{-1}) and direction the wind is coming from at Observatory Hill (SH) and Sydney Airport (BB) for each season.

		Rushcutters Bay				Walsh Bay				Sow & Pigs				Spit Bridge			
		10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d
No-wind	Active (%)	99.4	91.5	78.7	68.3	98.5	90.5	75.9	65.4	6.5	2.8	1.5	1.0	75.0	27.4	12.7	10.0
	Grounded (%)	0.4	2.0	4.3	6.0	0.9	2.1	5.0	7.2	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.2	0.2
	Escaped (%)	0.2	6.5	17.0	25.7	0.6	7.4	19.1	27.4	93.5	97.2	98.5	99.0	25.0	72.4	87.1	89.8
Northerly	Active (%)	98.3	77.0	58.7	46.1	97.7	79.5	62.5	49.6	13.1	4.8	3.0	2.4	61.6	34.4	25.9	20.3
	Grounded (%)	0.5	2.3	3.2	4.6	0.9	2.7	4.5	6.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.5
	Escaped (%)	1.2	20.7	38.1	49.3	1.4	17.8	33.0	44.4	86.8	95.1	96.9	97.5	38.2	65.3	73.8	79.2
Southerly	Active (%)	94.5	74.1	56.5	46.2	98.8	88.0	70.2	58.2	5.9	0.2	0	0	97.7	79.6	63.6	55.3
	Grounded (%)	0.4	2.4	4.1	5.8	0.8	2.6	4.4	6.6	0	0	0	0	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.8
	Escaped (%)	5.1	23.5	39.4	48.0	0.4	9.4	25.4	35.2	94.1	99.8	100	100	1.9	20.3	35.7	43.9
Easterly	Active (%)	97.5	81.9	68.4	56.5	98.1	86.3	71.9	61.8	7.3	2.3	1.4	1.0	71.1	45.1	32.1	26.8
	Grounded (%)	0.5	2.8	4.2	6.3	1.0	2.1	4.2	5.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.6	1.0	1.6
	Escaped (%)	2.0	15.3	27.4	37.2	0.9	11.6	23.9	33.2	92.6	97.5	98.4	98.7	28.4	54.3	66.9	71.6
Westerly	Active (%)	96.4	73.4	54.7	43.9	97.8	89.3	74.4	60.9	17.9	5.8	3.6	2.9	86.9	56.3	39.3	31.1
	Grounded (%)	0.3	0.9	4.8	3.2	1.5	3.6	6.0	7.6	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.8	1.2	1.6
	Escaped (%)	3.3	25.7	43.5	52.9	0.7	7.1	19.6	31.5	82.1	94.1	96.3	97.0	12.9	42.9	59.5	67.3
Northeasterly	Active (%)	97.3	77.1	58.5	46.3	97.2	77.5	59.1	46.2	13.7	5.1	2.6	1.8	23.1	7.2	4.9	3.2
	Grounded (%)	0.7	1.8	3.6	4.8	1.2	2.5	4.5	6.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3
	Escaped (%)	2.0	21.1	37.9	48.9	1.6	20.0	36.4	47.8	86.2	94.7	97.0	97.8	76.7	92.6	94.8	96.5

Table 2: Summary of active, grounded and escaped particles after 10 d, 30 d, 60 d and 90 d for each of the wind scenarios and locations seeded in Sydney Harbour.

		Georges River				Cooks River				Sydney Airport				Port Botany				Kurnell			
		10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d	10 d	30 d	60 d	90 d
No-wind	Active (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	75.7	46.1	100	84.6	51.9	37	76.2	38.4	21.7	15.5	100	100	99.9	99.7
	Grounded (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	0	0	0.2	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
	Escaped (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	24.2	53.7	0	15.4	47.9	62.8	23.8	61.6	78.3	84.5	0	0	0	0
Northerly	Active (%)	100	95.4	90.7	84.2	100	86.4	62.3	49.7	100	75.9	58.9	46.5	99.8	70.9	47.7	34.7	99.9	99.9	94.8	92.9
	Grounded (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	0	0	0	0.1	0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3
	Escaped (%)	0	4.6	9.3	15.8	0	13.6	37.6	50.1	0	24.1	41.1	53.4	0.2	29	52.1	65.1	0	0	4.9	6.8
Southerly	Active (%)	100	59.3	13.5	8.0	100	100	93.1	78.2	92.2	54.9	31.9	19.1	78.8	47.7	29.2	18.5	22.7	10.6	6.5	3.9
	Grounded (%)	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0	0	0.1	0	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0	0	0
	Escaped (%)	0	40.6	86.4	91.9	0	0	6.9	21.7	7.8	45.0	67.8	80.6	21.1	52.2	70.7	81.4	77.3	89.4	93.5	96.1
Easterly	Active (%)	100	37.9	11.1	4.6	97.8	38.3	10.0	4.2	64.7	23.1	7.1	3.7	45.9	19.5	7.2	3.6	100	31.9	10.5	4.7
	Grounded (%)	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0	0.2	0.2	0.3
	Escaped (%)	0	62	88.8	95.3	2.1	61.2	89.5	95.3	35.2	76.8	92.5	96.2	54.1	80.3	92.6	96.2	0	67.9	89.3	95.0
Westerly	Active (%)	72.6	19.0	5.7	2.5	100	48.5	20.7	9.5	100	47.3	16.9	7.3	99.9	52.7	20.9	7.1	35.3	19.9	7.7	3.2
	Grounded (%)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0	0	0
	Escaped (%)	27.3	80.9	94.2	97.4	0	51.4	79.2	90.4	0	52.7	83.1	92.7	0.1	47.3	79.1	92.8	64.7	80.1	92.3	96.8
Northeasterly	Active (%)	100	44.9	21.2	10.1	100	61.5	26.5	14.1	74.6	38.1	16.2	7.8	74.9	41.4	21.4	11.1	100	55.9	25.5	13.0
	Grounded (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0	0	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0	0	0	0
	Escaped (%)	0	55.1	78.8	89.9	0	38.4	73.3	85.6	25.4	61.9	83.8	92.1	25.0	58.5	78.4	88.6	0	44.1	74.5	87.0

Table 3: Summary of active, grounded and escaped particles after 10 d, 30 d, 60 d and 90 d for each of the wind scenarios and locations seeded in Botany Bay.

Figure 1: Coastline of Sydney Harbour, Botany Bay and Port Hacking on the east coast of Australia. Location of the anemometers in BB and SH are marked.

Figure 2: Bathymetry of Sydney Harbour (Port Jackson). Locations in the figure are defined as: Parra-matta River (PR), Homebush Bay (HB), Sydney Harbour Bridge (SHB), Walsh Bay (WB), Rushcutters Bay (RB), South Head (STH), Middle Head (MH), Sow & Pigs (SP), North Head (NH), Middle Harbour (MHB), the Spit Bridge (SB), and Bantry Bay (BN).

Figure 3: Bathymetry of Botany Bay. Locations in the figure are defined as: Georges River (GR), Cooks River (CR), Sydney Airport (A), Port Botany (PB), La Perouse (LP), Kurnell (K).

Figure 4: Water velocities in Sydney Harbour in the absence of wind forcing for: a) flood tide, b) high tide, c) ebb tide and d) low tide, where the phase of the tide is indicated by the tidal curve.

Figure 5: Difference in velocities (SH) when subjected to a 14.5 kmh^{-1} southerly wind compared to that experienced during the absence of wind forcing (Figure 4).

Figure 6: Comparison of the velocities at the entrance to SH (thin lines) and BB (dark lines) under the 6 wind scenarios. The dashed (solid) lines represent the north-south (east-west) component of velocity.

Figure 7: Water velocities in Botany Bay in the absence of wind forcing for: a) flood tide, b) high tide, c) ebb tide and d) low tide, where the phase of the tide is indicated by the tidal curve.

Figure 8: Difference in velocities (BB) when subjected to a 14.5 kmh^{-1} easterly wind compared to that experienced during the absence of wind forcing

Figure 9: Distributions of particles seeded at Walsh Bay (SH) when subjected to a 14.5 km h^{-1} north-easterly for a) 10 days, b) 30 days, c) 60 days and d) 90 days after seeding also showing the percentage of particles in the harbour remaining active, percentage of particles that have escaped the harbour, and percentage of particles that have entered land cells within the domain. Subfigures e) through h) show the corresponding probability distributions of finding any given particle within a 1 km box centred at that location at any given time within the specified time period whilst the particle is inside the harbour and active. Locations where particles have entered land cells are denoted by asterisk (*) and the location of seeding is shown by the square (■).

Figure 10: Distributions of particles seeded at Port Botany (BB) when subjected to a 14.5 kmh^{-1} northerly for a) 10 days, b) 30 days, c) 60 days and d) 90 days after seeding also showing the percentage of particles in the bay remaining active, percentage of particles that have escaped and percentage of particles that have entered land cells within the domain. Subfigures e) through h) show the corresponding probability distributions of finding any given particle within a 1 km box centred at that location at any given time within the specified time period whilst the particle is inside the harbour and active. Locations where particles have entered land cells are denoted by asterisk (*) and the location of seeding is shown by the square (■).

Figure 11: Total concentration of particles remaining in SH for particles seeded at a) Walsh Bay, b) Rushcutters Bay, c) the Spit Bridge and d) Sow & Pigs.

Figure 12: Total concentration of particles remaining in BB for particles seeded at a) Georges River, b) Cooks River, c) Port Botany d) Sydney Airport and e) Kurnell.

Figure 13: Evolution of the age of water in Sydney Harbour at a) Homebush Bay, b) The Spit Bridge, c) Walsh Bay and d) Rushcutters Bay. Note that the data has been smoothed to show the average age within the tidal cycle.

Figure 14: Evolution of the age of water in Botany Bay at a) Georges River, b) Cooks River, c) Port Botany, d) Sydney Airport and e) Kurnell. Note that the data has been smoothed to show the average age within the tidal cycle.

Figure 15: Age of water in SH 1 year (365 d) after the initialisation of the age tracer (left). Anomaly in the age of the water.

Figure 16: Anomaly in the age of the water in SH after one year.

Figure 17: Age of water in BB 1 year (365 d) after the initialisation of the age tracer (left).

Figure 18: Anomaly in the age of the water in BB after one year.